

Initial State and Transition State Solvation Trends for Base Hydrolysis of Iron(II) Complexes of Bidentate Schiff Base Imine Ligands in MeOH-H₂O Mixtures

EZZ-ELDIN A. ABU-GHARIB

Science & Math. Center, P. O. Box 4341, Riyadh 11491, Saudi Arabia

Manuscript received 5 August 1992, revised 8 June 1993, accepted 27 July 1993

Iron(II) complexes of bidentate Schiff base imine ligands derived from 2-pyridinecarboxaldehyde, 2-acetylpyridine or 2-benzoylpyridine and 1-phenylethylamine have been prepared. The effect of added co-solvent methanol on the solvation of these Fe^{II} complex cations has been investigated. The trends in transfer chemical potentials are discussed in terms of the nature of the coordinated ligands and are compared with those for a selection of other Fe^{II} complex ions. Rate constants at 298 K are reported for base hydrolysis of Fe^{II} complexes in methanol-water mixtures. The kinetic results have been split into the effect of solvent on the initial and transition states. The results indicate that the initial state is stabilised to a lesser degree than the transition state with small increase in the rate constant as co-solvent methanol increases. The overall trend in rate constant is controlled by the greater effect of solvent on the transition state.

Considerable insight is afforded into the factors controlling rates of chemical reactions in binary aqueous mixtures. Recently we studied reactions involving inorganic and organic compounds in methanol-water mixtures. Rate constants for reaction between these compounds and hydroxide ions in aqueous methanol mixtures are sensitive to the hydrophobic compounds and mole fraction of organic solvent. The dependence of rate constants on solvent composition reflects underlying dependence in standard chemical potentials of initial and transition states. Therefore an analysis of these kinetic data involves the calculation of transfer chemical potentials for ions in binary aqueous methanol system¹⁻³.

The aim of this work is to extend the investigation of the effect of added co-solvent on the solubilities of Fe^{II} complexes of bidentate Schiff base imine ligands, and to know about these complexes for transfer from water to methanol-water mixtures, and establish which ligands lead to stabilisation, and which lead to destabilisation on transfer. The study is also intended to analyse reactivity trends for base

hydrolysis of Fe^{II} complexes of bidentate Schiff base imine ligands in methanol-water mixtures into initial state and transition state trends and illustrate the usefulness of the transfer parameters. Therefore an attempt has been made to estimate the effect of solvent on the initial state, and the corresponding effect of solvent on the transition state is calculated using both kinetic and initial state data.

The existence of stable low-spin Fe^{II} complexes of 2,2-bipyridyl [Fe(bipy)₃]²⁺ and 1,1-phenanthroline [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ is well known⁴. The di-imine moiety which is characteristic of these ligands, is also present in Schiff bases derived from pyridine-2-carbaldehyde or 2-ketones and 1-phenylethylamine. The complexes have been syn-

R = H (bsbh)
R = Me (bsbm)
R = Ph (bsbp)

thesised by reaction of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde, 2-acetylpyridine or 2-benzoylpyridine and 1-phenylethylamine with Fe^{II}.

Results and Discussion

If a given salt is sparingly soluble in water and in aqueous organic mixture, the ratio of solubilities leads directly to the transfer chemical potentials for the salt. The Fe^{II}-Schiff base salts of the perchlorate are sparingly soluble in water and in methanol-water mixtures. They are, thus, suitable for the estimation of transfer chemical potentials of Fe^{II} complex salts from water into such mixtures. The solubilities of [Fe(bsbh)₃](ClO₄)₂, [Fe(bsbm)₃](ClO₄)₂ and [Fe(bsbp)₃](ClO₄)₂ in aqueous solutions at 298 K increase when co-solvent methanol is added. The solubility data are expressed (Table 1) as transfer parameters for the salts on concentration scale, describing the change in standard chemical potentials of these salts on transfer from aqueous solution to aqueous methanol mixtures⁵. Thus

$$\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\#(MX; c\text{-scale, SIn; } P; T) = -RT \ln \left[\frac{k_{sp}(X_2)}{k_{sp}(aq)} \right] \quad (1)$$

where 'SIn' means 'in solution state', at ambient pressure *P* and temperature *T*.

The transfer chemical potential of a salt is obtained which, together with estimates of single ion quantities for one ion, leads to the transfer parameter, for the counter ion^{3,6}. Thus for the salt of the type M_mX_n, where Mⁿ⁺ is cation and X^{m-} is anion,

$$\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\#(MX) = m\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\#(M^{n+}) + n\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\#(X^{m-}) \quad (2)$$

Transfer chemical potentials for these salts were calculated on the assumption that the ratio of the molar activity coefficient was unity in all cases. As discussed earlier², in the present context this is probably satisfactory [*Z* + *Z*−] ≤ 3 using the transfer chemical potentials for the various cationic complexes derived on the (TATB)⁷ and (TPTB)⁸ assumption. Either of these assumptions forms the basis of recent treatments of the thermodynamic properties of ions in binary aqueous mixtures.

Table 1 reveals the results of solubilities of the Fe^{II} complex salts as perchlorate. It also includes estimates of δ_m (aq → x₂) μ[#] complex cations derived from these solubilities using δ_m (aq → x₂) μ[#] (ClO₄) as reported by Abraham *et al.*⁸, who used δ_m (aq → x₂) μ[#] (Ph₄P⁺ or Ph₄As⁺) = δ_m (aq → x₂) μ[#] (Ph₄B⁺) assumption. The trends of the transfer chemical potentials for these Fe^{II}-Schiff base imine complex cations are compared⁹ with [Fe(N₂DMG)₃]²⁺, [Fe(bipy)₃]²⁺ and [Fe(phen)₃]²⁺ in Fig 1. The results can mainly be rationalised in terms of overall charge and ligand number for each complex and hydrophobic nature of the present ligands. This Fig. 1 provide a good illustration of the effects of ligand bulk. The smallest complex cation [Fe(N₂DMG)₃]²⁺ shows little preference for water or methanol, but increasing bulk leads to a preference for methanol until, with the phenanthroline ligand, the stabilisation of the Fe^{II} complex cation on transfer to methanol-rich mixtures.

TABLE 1—SOLUBILITY OF COMPLEX SALTS AND TRANSFER CHEMICAL POTENTIALS OF COMPLEX CATIONS AT 298 K (MOLAR SCALE)*

MeOH vol. %	[Fe(bsbh) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂		[Fe(bsbm) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂		[Fe(bsbp) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂	
	×10 ³ Soly. mol dm ⁻³	δ _m μ [#] (cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	×10 ³ Soly. mol dm ⁻³	δ _m μ [#] (cation) kJ mol ⁻¹	×10 ³ Soly. mol dm ⁻³	δ _m μ [#] (cation) kJ mol ⁻¹
0	1.06	—	0.77	—	0.42	—
20	1.47	-2.4	1.12	-2.7	0.78	-4.49
40	2.62	-6.6	2.19	-7.5	1.68	-10.1
60	3.81	-12.8	3.39	-14.2	3.31	-18.5

*Complexes assumed anhydrous as decompose on warming : δ_m μ[#] (ClO₄) from Ref. 8.

Fig. 1. Transfer chemical potentials for iron(II) complexes of bidentate imine ligands.

Transfer chemical potentials of the Fe^{II} -Schiff base imine complex cations fit into the pattern based on ligand bulk and the relative hydrophilic/hydrophobic ligands. Hydrophobic ligands, such as heterocyclic Schiff bases lead to stabilisation as methanol content increases. Phenyl group is considerably more hydrophobic than methyl group and proton; thus, the results show preferential solvation by methanol which becomes more rich as ligand size increases. With increase in the ligand size, parallel hydrophobic character develops, resulting from both replacement of proton, methyl and phenyl group.

Kinetics of the reaction between the iron(II) complexes and hydroxide ion were followed spectrophotometrically at 298 K. The observed first order rate constants as a function of hydroxide concentration are reported in Table 2.

The dependence of rate on hydroxide ion concentration is shown in equation (3),

$$d[\text{Fe}(\text{L-L})_3]^{2+}/dt = (k_1 + k_2 [\text{OH}^-])[\text{Fe}(\text{L-L})_3]^{2+} \quad (3)$$

where k_1 is the first order rate constant for aquation reaction and k_2 the second order rate constant. For solution where $[\text{OH}^-] \gg$ complex, the first order rate constant becomes

$$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{OH}^-] \quad (4)$$

TABLE 2—RATE CONSTANTS FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF COMPLEX CATIONS IN AQUEOUS MIXTURES AS A FUNCTION OF VOL. % OF MeOH AT 298 K

MeOH vol. %	NaOH (mol dm ⁻³)			
	0.066	0.133	0.200	0.266
	[Fe(bsbh) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂			
	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
0	1.2	1.3	1.4	1.5
20	1.6	1.7	1.9	2.1
40	2.3	2.6	2.9	3.2
60	2.9	3.3	3.6	4.0
	[Fe(bsbm) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂			
	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
0	1.6	1.9	2.3	2.6
20	2.1	2.5	2.9	2.4
40	2.8	3.4	4.0	4.5
60	3.4	4.2	4.8	5.5
	[Fe(bsbp) ₃](ClO ₄) ₂			
	10 ⁴ k _{obs} (s ⁻¹)			
0	2.2	3.0	3.7	4.5
20	2.7	3.6	4.5	5.4
40	3.6	4.7	5.9	7.2
60	4.5	6.0	6.9	—

values of k_1 and k_2 computed from a least-mean-squares analysis of the dependence of the observed first order rate constants on base concentration at each aqueous methanol proportion are presented in Table 3.

TABLE 3—FIRST AND SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (k_1 , k_2) AND FREE ENERGIES OF ACTIVATION ($\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$) FOR BASE HYDROLYSIS OF Fe^{II} COMPLEX CATIONS IN BINARY AQUEOUS MIXTURES

MeOH vol. %	10 ⁴ k ₁ s ⁻¹	10 ² k ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹	$\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ mol ⁻¹
0	1.50	1.09	—
20	1.80	1.35	-0.53
40	2.35	1.80	-1.42
60	3.00	2.18	-1.72
	[Fe(bsbm) ₃] ²⁺		
0	1.25	0.49	—
20	1.60	0.68	-0.81
40	2.25	0.83	-1.31
60	2.75	1.02	-1.82
	[Fe(bsbp) ₃] ²⁺		
0	1.00	0.23	—
20	1.35	0.33	-0.94
40	2.00	0.45	-1.71
60	2.55	0.56	-2.26

The second order path (rate constant k_2), which is the dominant path at moderate concentrations of strong nucleophiles of this type, can be assigned with confidence to a bimolecular

process, but whether the initial site of attack is the iron atom or some position in the heteroaromatic coordinated ligand is a question of debate. There are two possible sites for nucleophilic hydroxide attack on complexes of this type, at the metal or at the ligand; chelate ring-opening or S_N1CB pathways are also possible¹⁰. Our results do not provide any direct mechanistic evidence, but since the central azomethine carbon atom of the ligand may be considered to be more electropositive (aliphatic moiety), it is conceivable that the hydroxide attacks at this site in the complexes as shown in Scheme 1. As species $[Fe(L-L)_2(OH_2)_2]^{2+}$ will be high-spin, they in turn will dissociate very quickly.

Scheme 1

For a solution which is dilute in reactant, the rate constant k_2 is related, using transition state theory¹, to the molar Gibbs function of activation (ΔG^\ddagger) expressed on the concentration scale, temperature T and mole fraction x_2 , hence

$$\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \Delta G^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; T) = -RT \ln [k_2(x_2; T)/k_2(aq; T)] \quad (5)$$

where $k_2(aq; T)$ and $k_2(x_2; T)$ are the second order rate constants in aqueous solution and in a mixture. We have further assumed that the transmission coefficient is unity and/or independent of solvent composition. The change in the activation barrier $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ for the three complexes from water to aqueous methanol are given in Table 3.

The activation quantity $\delta_m \Delta G^\ddagger$ can be related to the chemical potentials of the transition state $\delta_m \mu^\ddagger$, the Fe^{II} complex cation $\delta_m \mu^\ddagger M^{2+}$ and the incoming ionic nucleophile $\delta_m \mu^\ddagger(OH^-)$. In other words, combination of kinetic data, solubility data and transfer chemical potentials yields the effect of solvent on the transition state, $\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; SIn; P; T)$, hence

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; SIn; T) = & \delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \Delta G^\ddagger (c\text{-scale}; SIn; P; T) \\ & + \delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger(M^{2+}; c\text{-scale}; SIn; P; T) \\ & + \delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger(OH^-; c\text{-scale}; SIn; P; T) \quad (6) \end{aligned}$$

Here we use the ambient pressure P , and $T = 298$ K.

The details of the initial state-transition state analysis for hydroxide attack at the Fe^{II} Schiff base imine complex cations are presented in Table 4. The results for $[Fe(bsbh)_3]^{2+}$ complex are depicted in Fig. 2. The pattern shows predominant role played solvation of the hydrophobic ligands both in the initial and transition states. In these systems there are small change in rate constants and relatively small change in $\delta_m(aq \rightarrow x_2) \mu^\ddagger(OH^-)$ ⁸. However, one sees slight destabilisation of the hydroxide ion and marked stabilisation of the complex ion acting in opposition but still resulting in a marked stabilisation of the initial state and, indeed, of the transition state as the methanol content of the mixture increases. However, the analysis of the reactivity trends of the Fe^{II}

Fig. 2. Initial state-transition state analysis for base hydrolysis of $[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbh})_3]^{2+}$ in MeOH-H₂O mixtures.

complexes and hydroxide ion shows the initial state and the transition state which are stabilised on increasing the methanol content with small increase in the rate constant. This is due to the slightly greater effect of solvent on the transition state.

TABLE 4—INITIAL STATE-TRANSITION STATE ANALYSIS OF SOLVENT EFFECTS ON REACTIVITY TRENDS

Parameters*	MeOH vol. %		
	20	40	60
	$[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbh})_3]^{2+} + \text{OH}^-$		
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{cation})$	-2.4	-6.6	-12.8
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{is})$	-2.6	-6.5	-11.2
$\delta_m \Delta G^\#$	-0.5	-1.4	-1.7
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{ts})$	-3.1	-7.9	-12.9
	$[\text{Fe}(\text{bshh})_3]^{2+} + \text{OH}^-$		
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{cation})$	-2.7	-7.5	-14.2
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{is})$	-2.9	-7.4	-12.6
$\delta_m \Delta G^\#$	-0.8	-1.3	-1.8
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{ts})$	-3.7	-8.7	-14.4
	$[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbp})_3]^{2+} + \text{OH}^-$		
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{cation})$	-4.5	-10.1	-18.5
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{is})$	-4.7	-10.0	-16.9
$\delta_m \Delta G^\#$	-0.9	-1.7	-2.3
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{ts})$	-5.6	-11.7	-19.2
$\delta_m \mu^\#(\text{OH}^-)$	-0.2	0.1	1.6

* All units in kJ mol⁻¹.

Experimental

Laboratory reagent grade FeCl₂·4H₂O, pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde, 2-acetylpyridine, 2-benzoylpyridine, 1-phenylethylamine, ethanol and KI were used.

Stoichiometric proportions of ethanolic solutions of the appropriate precursors of the required Schiff base ligand refluxed for 1–2 h. To this Schiff base solution was added the stoichiometric amount of FeCl₂·4H₂O dissolved in ethanol containing a few drops of acetic acid (this inhibits oxidation of the Fe^{II}). The reaction solution was allowed to stand at room temperature until full development of the blue colour (60 min).

Appropriate amount of KI dissolved in small quantity of water was then added and the mixture kept at -5° for 2 h. The resulting dark violet microcrystalline precipitate was washed with water and diethyl ether. The complex salts showed a characteristic band at 570–580 nm and the molar absorptivity values being 3.36–3.70 × 10³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, which disappeared completely when base hydrolysis was complete. Microanalysis data of the complex salts are shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEX SALTS

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
	Fe	C	N	H
$[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbh})_3]_2$	6.05 (6.19)	51.52 (51.77)	9.18 (9.29)	4.54 (4.65)
$[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbm})_3]_2$	5.95 (6.11)	55.33 (55.02)	9.22 (9.17)	4.15 (5.24)
$[\text{Fe}(\text{bsbp})_3]_2$	5.68 (5.57)	69.54 (69.80)	8.43 (8.57)	5.62 (5.51)

Kinetics and solubility : Kinetics of base hydrolysis were followed using 10 mm silica cell in the thermostated cell holder compartment of a Pye-Unicam 8-100 spectrophotometer. Base hydrolysis was monitored for every complex at 298 K. First order plots were linear for at least 2.5 half-lives. The kinetic measurements of the loss of absorbance at the fixed λ_{max} was followed by the formation of a precipitate in the reaction solution. Ferric hydroxide and possibly dissociated ligand, particularly at higher volume percentages of water, were precipitated. Initial concentration of the complexes was 4 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ and the hydroxide ion concentration was in the range upto 0.226 mol

dm^{-3} . The ionic strength was made up to 0.33 mol dm^{-3} with sodium chloride.

The sparingly soluble complex salts as perchlorate was prepared by double-decomposition in aqueous-alcohol mixtures. Solubility was measured by agitating a generous excess of the solid with the appropriate solvent mixture in thermostated vessel. The sample was centrifuged, an aliquot of saturated solution removed and the solution diluted as necessary. Concentrations of salts were measured using the absorbances at reported characteristic wavelength.

References

1. M. J. BLANDAMER and J. BURGESS, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1980, **31**, 93; J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *J. Chem. Res. (S)*, 1984, 8; *J. Chem. Res. (M)*, 1984, 275; E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Bull. Soc. Chem. Fr.*, 1988, 916.
2. M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 193.
3. A. A. EL-SAMAHY, E. A. ABU-GHARIB, A. ELTAHER, R. EL-KHATIB and J. BURGESS, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1992, in press.
4. F. BLAU, *Chem. Ber.*, 1888, **21**, 1077; *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1889, **10**, 375; 1889, **19**, 647; F. BASOLO and R. G. PERSON, "Mechanisms of Inorganic Reactions", 2nd ed., Wiley, New York, 1967, Chap. 3.
5. S. MURAKAMI, R. TANAKA and R. FUJISHIRO, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1974, **3**, 71; J. DATTA and K. K. KUNDU, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1983, **61**, 625; J. E. DESNOYERS, G. PERRON, L. AVEDIKIAN and J. P. MOREL, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1976, **5**, 631.
6. J. BURGESS and E. A. ABU-GHARIB, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 234.
7. C. TISSIER, *Compt. Rend.*, 1978, **286C**, 35.
8. M. H. ABRAHAM, T. HILL, H. C. LING, R. A. SCHULZ and R. A. C. WATT, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1984, **80**, 489.
9. E. A. ABU-GHARIB, M. J. BLANDAMER, J. BURGESS, N. GOSAL, P. GUARDADO, F. SANCHEZ and C. D. HUBBARD, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1984, **9**, 306.
10. R. D. GILLARD, D. W. KNIGHT and P. A. WILLIAMS, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1980, **5**, 321; R. D. GILLARD, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **16**, 67; 1983, **50**, 303.